

Engineers working as a team: socio-emotional and intercultural skills for multicultural environments

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Abstract

This workshop consists of an activity that aims to help engineering students to develop socio-emotional and intercultural skills. Through a usual situation for engineers at the beginning of their career, the participant will have the opportunity to experience a situation in which it will be necessary to work as a team, communicate, negotiate, and deal with colleagues of different nationalities.

Keywords: Teamwork skills; Socioemotional and intercultural skills; Engineering Education; Active Learning.

1 Introduction

Engineering students need more than technical knowledge to face the demands of the 21st century (Downey et al., 2006; Passow, 2012). They also need to develop lifelong learning skills, such as socio-emotional and intercultural skills. Socio-emotional skills will enable future engineers to understand the social, moral and human values of a society. This will help them to work as a team, negotiate, manage, empathize, and deal better with colleagues, customers and the general public. Developing cross-cultural skills will provide the future engineer with the competence needed to work on complex global projects, immigrate to find work, collaborate and compete with colleagues of other nationalities, and work for international companies. Engineering schools are exploring ways to support and develop socio-emotional and intercultural competences in students. However, to date, studies on this subject are not as abundant as one would like (Ndubuisi et al., 2020).

Seat, Parsons & Poppen (2001) brought that there is no secret that the quality of interpersonal, communication, and teaming skills in engineering graduates—termed *performance skills*—is of concern to both industry employers and engineering educators. These skills include communication abilities, interpersonal interaction, conflict mediation, team performance, understanding of technical culture, and sensitivity toward diverse populations due to race, ethnicity, gender, and socio-economic standing.

Besides learning how to work in teams, engineering students need to learn how to establish a collaborative culture in their future workplace and how to deal/communicate/negotiate with people from different countries and cultures (Josefsson, 2010; Rico-García & Fielden Burns, 2019).

2 Activities

The activities in this workshop are:

- (i) Getting to know each other.
- (ii) Dividing the participants in pairs.
- (iii) Developing the activity:

Part 1: a large company sends two engineers (one from country A and one from country B) to work on the construction of two bridges and an underwater tunnel between Cardiff and Weston-super-Mare in the United Kingdom. For that, a two-bedroom apartment will be made available where they will live for a year. The apartments have basic items, but most of the furniture is not available. Each of the engineers will receive a sum of 2000 euros to equip and furnish the apartment, considering their personal and cultural characteristics.

Part 2: upon arriving in the UK, the two engineers are informed that there has been a logistical problem in the allocation of the apartments, and they will have to share the apartment with two more engineers from country C and country D. Therefore, they will have to divide themselves into pairs that will occupy each dormitory and will have to redo the shopping list, because due to this relocation, each of the four engineers will receive only 1200 euros.

- (iv) Presenting the results obtained by the different teams.
- (v) Reflecting on the results obtained by the different teams.

3 Material needed for the workshop

Each participant must bring their notebook to the workshop. The workshop organizers will provide office supplies.

4 Expected results

By the end of this workshop, we expect that the participants can recognize that besides having skills to work in teams, future engineers need to be prepared to share a living space with co-workers, negotiate, manage, empathize and deal better with colleagues, work on complex global projects, immigrate to find work, collaborate and compete with colleagues of other nationalities, and work for international companies, among other skills that are important for academic and professional life.

5 References

- Downey, G. L., Lucena, J. C., Moskal, B. M., Parkhurst, R., Bigley, T., Hays, C., ..., & Nichols-Belo, A. (2006). The globally competent engineer: Working effectively with people who define problems differently. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 95(2), 107-122.
- Josefsson, T. (2010). Intercultural Competence in Engineering Education. 7th CDIO. http://www.cdio.org/files/document/file/T2A_Paper_2.pdf
- Passow, H. J. (2012) Which ABET Competencies Do Engineering Graduates Find Most Important in their Work? *Journal of Engineering Education*, 101(1), 95–118.
- Seat, E., Parsons, J. R., & Poppen, W. A. (2001). Enabling engineering performance skills: A program to teach communication, leadership, and teamwork. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 90(1), 7-12.
- Ndubuisi, A., Khan, R., Marzi, E., & Edun, O. (2020, October). A KCI Approach to Promote Intercultural Competencies for International Virtual Engineering Student Teams (InVEST). In 2020 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE) (pp. 1-5). IEEE..
- Rico-García, M., & Fielden Burns, L. V. (2019). Intercultural communication in engineering studies: a key competence in global labour markets. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 45(6), 833-853.